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THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL MODELING INNOVATION AND TRENDS DEVELOPEMENT IN THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE MARKET OF TOURIST SERVICES: REGIONAL ASPECT

The object of research is the development of competitiveness of the market of tourist services. The study is based on the development and implementation of innovations in the market of tourist services, through the prism of a new philosophy of the tourism industry, including travel, which is based primarily on safety, protection and health, growth and balance of human needs. The article highlights and substantiates the priorities of the gradual exit from the crisis of COVID-19 and trends in the competitiveness of the market of tourist services, focusing on the regional aspect. The state and main characteristics of the tourist and recreational potential of domestic tourism are analyzed, on the example of the Lviv region (Ukraine). The main negative tendencies are singled out and the ways of their solution are substantiated.

The analysis of experience and perspective technologies of development of the tourist market of the region is carried out. It is characterized that the priority role in the attractiveness of the region is played by the tourist service, which forms the impression of the tourist product in general. Based on this, it is substantiated that there is a close interdependence between the service and the tourist product in the market of tourist services of Lviv region.

The understanding of cultural tourism through ethno-festivals as a mechanism of development of tourist services of the Lviv region is revealed. The system of ethno-festivals of Lviv region, which provide tourist attractiveness, is singled out. It is argued that the development of cultural tourism best promotes the uniqueness of customs, rituals, traditions and culture of the region. It is proved that ethno-festivals can be considered as a mechanism of effective promotion that promotes the development of tourist services in the Lviv region.

Emphasis is placed on the fact that domestic tourism and the values of sustainable development help to develop the economy and conserve resources. The mechanism optimization for improving the formation of competitiveness of the market of tourist services of the Lviv area by realization of safe tourism, development and modernization of tourist infrastructure, creation of tourist, infrastructural and innovation clusters, formation of economic logistics, active use of innovative technologies and marketing of tourist region is offered.

Keywords: *tourism industry, tourist service, tourist product, cultural tourism, competitive market of tourist services.*

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1. Introduction

In the current context of negative trends in the impact of the pandemic on the tourism industry. The lack of effective statistics further emphasizes the priority of tourism business development as an economic sector. The problem of formation and development of the market of tourist services as an important tool of economic self-regulation, provides dynamic correspondence of supply and demand and is a priority lever of development. Today, during the pandemic, the question arises of the possibility of the tourism sector in such a difficult socio-economic environment. It is important to responsibly revitalize the tourism sector, following the global recommendations of the World Tourism Organization, which are based. As a result, tourism will become stronger and more sustainable for sustainable development.

In this context, it is necessary to carefully study the state of the market of tourist services and development trends with the possibility of implementing an effective mechanism for optimizing and restoring the tourism sector.

In this context, it is necessary to carefully study the state of the market of tourist services and development trends. Analysis of the possibility of implementing an effective mechanism for improving and restoring the tourism sector. This is important for obtaining objective information about the market processes taking place in the field of tourist services. In order to develop effective steps to transform the tourist through the prism of effective public administration. As well as ensuring private-public partnership, promoting market self-regulation, promoting the trend of preserving the tourist uniqueness of our

country. This situation creates an increase in consumer demands for safety and quality of tourist services. In addition, there is a close and interdependent connection between the development of the market of tourist services in Ukraine and its regions. Improving the performance of an individual region and increasing its competitiveness will contribute to economic growth and strengthen the country's economy as a whole. The relevance of the study of the issue is also due to insufficient theoretical justification.

2. The object of research and its technological audit

The object of research is the development of competitiveness of the market of tourist services. The study is based on the development and implementation of innovations in the market of tourist services, through the prism of a new philosophy of the tourism industry, including travel, which is based primarily on safety, protection and health, growth and balance of human needs. The article highlights and substantiates the priorities of the gradual exit from the crisis of COVID-19 and trends in the competitiveness of the market of tourist services, focusing on the regional aspect. The state and main characteristics of the tourist and recreational potential of domestic tourism are analyzed, on the example of the Lviv region (Ukraine). The main negative tendencies are singled out and the ways of their solution are substantiated. One of the most problematic areas is not taking into account socio-economic changes and the prospects for the formation of competitiveness of tourist services in the Lviv region.

3. The aim and objectives of research

The aim of research is a scientific and practical understanding and justification of the formation and development of the market of tourist services on the example of Lviv region (Ukraine).

To achieve the aim of scientific research, the following objectives are identified:

1. To analyze the state and main characteristics of the tourist and recreational potential of domestic tourism on the example of the Lviv region.

2. To single out the mechanism of improvement of formation of competitiveness of the market of tourist services of the Lviv area according to requirements of the present.

4. Research of existing solutions of the problem

The tourism industry is one of the most important sectors that influence the general state of society, as well as the main trends of the world economy. According to the World Tourism Organization, the contribution of tourism to the world's gross domestic product, taking into account the indirect effect is 10 % [1]. It is convinced that all objective preconditions are necessary for the formation of the competitiveness of the tourist market, to become one of the most developed countries in the world in the field of tourism, thanks to its favorable geographical location, favorable climate, landscape, rich natural resources, cultural and historical heritage, etc. Such tourist and recreational potential makes it possible to become a world-

class tourist state and realizes the opportunity to fully meet the cognitive, recreational, communication, sports, spiritual and psychological needs of tourists, both domestic and foreign tourists. In our study, let's focus on the Lviv region, as the region is one of the five most attractive tourist destinations in Ukraine and is one of the most developed in the country in economic, tourist, cultural and scientific areas.

Today, in the situation of the COVID-19 pandemic, the vectors of the tourism industry are changing and the question of effective change in accordance with the requirements of the time arises. The development of the authors is interesting for our research [2, 3], which consider the pandemic shock and the impact of the pandemic crisis on the travel and tourism industry. The authors distinguish estimates of the impulse response of compound, general and idiosyncratic pandemic shocks, economic impact. But the question of the development of domestic tourism and industry in general remains.

Among the main areas of solving the problem of developing the competitiveness of the market of tourist services, identified in the resources of world periodicals, can be identified [4–6]. In particular, the authors [6] focus on the tools of balancing the system of indicators of quality, efficiency, organizational activities in the tourism industry as the development of sustainable tourism. However, scientists do not focus on the priority areas of domestic tourism, which is the basis for the development of sustainable tourism. In turn, the authors [5] emphasize the importance of implementing an effective tourism policy and effective business strategies that will ensure the recovery and development of the tourism industry. Although these allegations can be considered primarily through the regional aspect as a powerful mechanism for strategically restoring the country's tourist attractiveness in general.

The analysis of works [7, 8] allows to summarize that an important role in shaping the competitiveness of the market of tourist services is played by the diversity and uniqueness of historical, architectural and cultural monuments, natural conditions: healing mineral water and mud, favorable climatic, forest and water resources, colorful landscapes. In this context, considering the Lviv region [9], the positive in the geographical location of the Lviv region is that on its territory there is an international connection connecting Ukraine with Poland, Hungary, Slovakia, Romania. The northern part of the region lies within the Volyn Upland, Maly Polissya and Podil Upland, separated by the Dniester Valley from the Precarpathians. In addition, the uniqueness and diversity of recreational resources of the region, as well as the unique historical and cultural heritage create all opportunities to meet the cognitive, therapeutic, sports and spiritual needs of tourists, as well as contribute to research and development of domestic tourism. Due to this, in the Lviv region, the tourism sector is one of the strategic directions of socio-economic development of the region. Let's note that the priority is the development of cultural, educational, health, skiing, scientific and educational, religious, hunting, rural, environmental, ethnic, sports, health, business, leisure and entertainment tourism.

Interestingly, the availability of recreational resources, which are represented by medicinal mineral waters, therapeutic muds, favorable climatic, water and forest resources. Data analysis [9, 10] makes it possible to identify that the share of Lviv region in the total natural and recreational potential of Ukraine is about 5.4 %, and on this basis it is second only

to the Transcarpathian region. In the general structure of natural resources of Lviv region, recreational resources make up 14.6 % (the average in Ukraine is 9.5 %). Important components of the tourist attractiveness of the region are the diversity of landscapes (including mountain), dense river network, high forest cover (28.5 %, 7th place in Ukraine), rich balneological resources (7 types of mineral waters out of 8 known in balneology, more than 200 sources). There are 330 objects of the nature reserve fund in the region, including 1 nature reserve and 3 national parks. The share of protected areas in the total area of the region is about 5.6 % (7th place in Ukraine).

One of the defining components of the tourist attractiveness of Lviv region is the richness of historical and cultural resources. In particular, as noted in Lviv region is in first place among the regions of Ukraine in number, diversity and degree of preservation of historical and architectural heritage. In general, there are about 4,000 monuments of architecture and urban planning in the region, of which 794 are of national importance (19.3 % of the total in Ukraine). There are 1,817 sacred sites and churches (15 %) and 56 historic settlements (13.8 %) in the region. In addition, the region has the largest number of UNESCO World Heritage Sites.

It is also worth noting that in the Lviv region there are 5 historical and cultural reserves of national importance, namely in Lviv, Zhovkva, Belz, Nahujevychakhta, Tustan. Also museums-reserves: «Olesky Castle» and «Zolochiv Castle». Thus, the Lviv region is becoming more and more popular among tourists every year. This is also due to the fact that Lviv annually hosts more than 100 festivals, as well as more than 60 museums and 100 churches of various denominations, which are of great interest to all tourists, both from Ukraine and around the world. Tourists visit the region to see the beauty of nature, visit fascinating sights, enjoy gastronomic trends, walk the colorful streets of Lviv. Tourist attractiveness is a necessary condition for the development of the tourist market of Lviv region. In this context, let's draw attention to the need to expand the network of tourist and recreational facilities and tourist information centers, the formation of modern engineering, utilities, environmental infrastructure of tourist and recreational centers and resorts. It is also necessary to develop networks of tourist facilities, promote «tourist magnets» of the region and modernize tourist and recreational infrastructure.

An analysis of the scientific literature and a poll suggests that there is a direct relationship between the quality of the tourism product and the number of tourists who come to the country and return again. That is why, to increase the attractiveness of the tourist product, it is necessary to actively work on improving the quality of high-level tourist services, to diversify their range. For example, in the market of tourist services of Lviv region, a lot has already been done in this aspect. For example, more than 50 new tourist routes for active tourism have been developed. Namely: 19 hiking trails, 16 cycling routes and 21 ecological trails. Tourists are offered options for horseback riding, air tourism (paragliders, parachutes, hot air ballooning), water tourism (recreation on catamarans, kayaks, inflatable boats), skiing, extreme tourism (mountaineering, rope parks, airsoft, paintball). ATVs), fishing, spearfishing, zoos, farms, golf courses, ice rinks, etc. However, to overcome the crisis quarantine situation, it is necessary to ensure the sustainability of the tourism sector through public-

private partnerships, branding of the territory, effective promotion of domestic tourism.

Author of the work [11] confirms the importance of development of the tourist market is the preservation of architectural heritage and the development of creative industries. To achieve this aim, it is necessary to increase the attractiveness of architectural monuments for tourists, to restore architectural monuments. It is also important to conduct an inventory of traditional cultural heritage sites and activities aimed at preserving wooden and sacred architecture as one of the most important components of the tourist product. In context, it should be noted that from June 2020, the ancient castles of Lviv region [12] were transferred to the Ministry of Culture and Information Policy. In particular, Pidhoretsky, Olesky, Zolochiv castles, Pyatnychanska Tower, Capuchin monastery and St. Anthony's Church in the village of Olesko, as well as the Church of the Exaltation and St. Joseph in Pidhirtsi Now the maintenance and restoration of monuments will be carried out at the expense of the state budget and patrons. This creates a platform to use them for businesses in the creative industries. In particular, holding festivals, filming, advertising, TV series and other creative projects, which will provide an opportunity to turn the atmosphere, authenticity and entourage of Ukrainian historical culture into real tourist «magnets» of the region.

Analyzing the state of the tourist market of Lviv region, let's note that the effective development of the tourist and recreational sphere is also hampered by the lack of quality roads connecting popular tourist centers and facilities. It is necessary to reconstruct the most strategically important for the development of tourist and recreational activities of road sections, directly to such tourist centers as Slavske, Rozluch, Tysovets, Belz, etc. The potential of sports facilities and bases, ski centers, as well as green tourism is also important for the development of the tourism industry in the region. An important factor in the potential development of resorts is the still untapped natural sources of mineral and thermal waters. It is important to note that one of the most attractive destinations in the Lviv region «Golden Horseshoe of Lviv region» is in trouble. Restoration works are needed for the castle buildings, on the basis of which this tourist route will be formed.

The strategic direction of popularizing the tourist attractiveness tourist market is to present at various forums and exhibitions, which helps to establish links between foreign investors, business and government officials, in addition, the forum is a tool to improve the country's reputation in the international arena.

As noted in the work [11] ethnic festivals as a strategic tool of cultural tourism are a priority for the development of tourist attractiveness. It should be noted that a significant number of ethnic festivals take place in the Lviv region and every year more and more interested tourists attend various ethnocultural events. Thus, all ethno-festivals of Lviv region can be classified according to different main purpose. The most popular among tourists are the following [9, 10]:

– «Ethnofestival of Hospitality», the main purpose – to attract people, especially young people, to participate in folk art, practical acquaintance with the sources of authentic folklore, attracting attention to the study of folklore, its research;

- «Zashkiv – Source of Spirit» – the key idea of the festival – love for the Ukrainian land and its heroes – both past and present;
- Festival of Ukrainian medieval culture «Tu Stan!» – the center of attention of the festival is a rock city-fortress, where history comes to life and is filled with a bright mixture of colors, sounds and aromas of antiquity;
- art festival «PineFest» is held to disseminate and promote among young people and youth at the local level of arts and crafts;
- International Festival of Ukrainian Dance and Culture – presentation of all the variety of Ukrainian dance, music and songs from all over the world where Ukrainians live;
- Zakhidfest festival – one of the largest music festivals in Lviv region; International Festival of Contemporary Music «Contrasts», the concept of the festival is based on the desire to present contemporary Ukrainian music in the context of the world;
- music festival «Music in old Lviv» – aimed at showing the uniqueness of musical culture;
- International Folklore Festival «Ethnovyr», folk groups from around the world present the culture of their countries in Lviv;
- BookForum is the largest book, literary and cultural festival in Ukraine and Central and Eastern Europe;
- «Christmas in Lviv» – here it is special and unusual, and so on.

Ethno festivals are quite popular, colorful and atmospheric. However, it is necessary today in the new realities of the time to introduce innovative mechanisms for promotion and holding of such events in compliance with all safety requirements to attract tourists.

Thus, the results of the analysis allow to conclude that quality travel services create an impression and form the attractiveness of a tourist product in the market of tourist services. High quality, safety and comfort of service attract tourists and encourage them to come back again and again. Unresolved parts of the overall problem are the implementation of innovation and prospects for the formation of competitiveness of tourist services on the example of Lviv region.

5. Methods of research

The work is based on general scientific and special research methods, in particular:

- system analysis to identify trends in the formation and development of the market of tourist services on the example of Lviv region (Ukraine) and its main mechanisms, factors, principles and functional characteristics;
- method of logical generalization is used for theoretical substantiation of ways of improvement and specification of the categorical apparatus of features of formation and development of the market of tourist services;
- fundamental method of cognition, to highlight the role of services in increasing the attractiveness of the tourist product and the specifics of ethno-festival tourism as a mechanism for the development of tourist services in the Lviv region, their systematization in the direction of improvement;
- synergetic approach to determine trends in the market of tourist services in the Lviv region.

6. Research results

In the context of the changes caused by the pandemic, it is finally necessary to focus on the development of domestic tourism, so that it is possible to rest safely and comfortably. It is convinced that the leading strategic goal of Lviv region to overcome the crisis quarantine situation is a new philosophy of domestic tourism and the values of sustainable development based on the implementation of safety, quality, innovation and improvement of competitiveness. Namely, the development of tourist infrastructure, creative industries, preservation of architectural heritage and improving the quality of the tourist product.

In the process of researching the issue, let's conduct a survey on the state and prospects of the tourism sector in Lviv region. The sample of respondents consists of a circle of stakeholders and those who responded to the questionnaire. According to which, to the question «Do you need changes in the promotion of domestic tourism and the introduction of innovative approaches to optimize the tourism market?», most respondents answered unequivocally (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Distribution of respondents' opinions on the need to introduce innovative approaches to optimizing the tourism market

The analysis of scientific and practical literature and the results of the sociological survey gives grounds to assert that the introduction of innovation will conceptually meet the needs of tourists and the socio-economic needs of the tourism industry in general.

An important role in the process of optimizing the market of tourist services should be given to innovations, as well as the development of the market of tourist services of Lviv region through tourist products. The creation and promotion of new tourist products is no less important than the development of a network of tourist facilities and the improvement of tourist and recreational infrastructure for the development of the tourist industry. They must be high quality, competitive, meet the requirements of tourists, while using all domestic resources, cross-border opportunities. The analysis of scientific and practical literature made it possible to identify priority ways to optimize the market of tourist services in the Lviv region. Respondents also determine the need for innovation and sustainability of tourism. To the question «Which of the following ways to optimize the tourism market do you consider the most effective way out of the crisis in the region?» as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The results of a survey on ways to optimize the tourism market: 1 – implementation of safe hospitality; 2 – development of a roadmap for overcoming the crisis caused by a pandemic; 3 – competitive human resources; 4 – digitalization; 5 – creating an effective integrated mobile application; 6 – marketing technologies; 7 – receiving grants; 8 – branding the territory; 9 – other

Let’s analyze the results in more detail.

The main trend of preserving the tourism sector is the implementation of safe hospitality in compliance with all requirements and the implementation of the best European protocols for safe travel. Currently, quality, safety and comfort are a priority in the choice of tourists. Thus, during the survey and determining the degree of agreement with the following statement: «Implementation of safe hospitality in compliance with all established World Health Organization (WHO) requirements will promote demand for the tourist product and increase travel activity» respondents made the following choice as shown in Table 1.

Table 1

The results of a sociological survey on the impact of tourism safety on increasing demand for tourism products

No.	Answer options	Type of professional activity							
		Tourist		Local government official		Student		Total	
	(amount/percentage)	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
1	Strongly agree	110	61	14	70	130	87	254	72.57
2	I agree rather than disagree	54	30	1	5	11	7	66	18.86
3	Difficult to answer	6	9	2	10	4	3	12	3.42
4	Rather disagree	0	0	1	5	2	1.33	3	0.86
5	Disagree	0	0	1	5	1	0.65	2	0.57
6	I completely disagree	0	0	1	5	2	1.33	3	0.86

The results of the survey allow to note that the majority of respondents, namely 72 % agree with the statement that it is the security of hospitality that will contribute to the demand for the tourist product and increase the activity of travel. In this context, the project of the National Tourist Organization of Ukraine #SafeTravels Contest is useful and interesting. The project is implemented on a partnership basis to promote the implementation of the Global Initiative World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) «SafeTravels» and reduce the negative effects of the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic in the field of tourism and hospitality in Ukraine.

The use of the SafeTravels brand by businesses allows tourists to identify locations, attractions and companies around the world as having adopted and implemented global standardized health and hygiene protocols to ensure that tourists travel safely.

It is also important to develop a roadmap for overcoming the crisis situation in the region using effective promotion of domestic tourism, digitalization and marketing of tourist resources of Lviv region. According to the strategic analysis of the tourist and recreational sphere of the region, it is possible to determine the priorities of development and modernization of the tourist infrastructure, which will ensure the improvement of the tourist market.

It should be noted that several projects for the development of bicycle tourism have already been developed and are being implemented in the Lviv region, in particular [9, 10]: projects «Velokarpatia: development of infrastructure for cycling tourism in the Lviv region» Bryukhovychi – Domazhyr Bear Shelter (designated in the part to the village of Bryukhovychi). «Rove Love Roztocze – together across borders» is implemented within the Roztocze region by 6 partners, 3 Polish and 3 Ukrainian: GminaZamość, Lublin Voivodeship, Roztocze National Park, Yavoriv National Nature Park, Department of Ecology and Natural Resources and Association of Local Governments (AOMS) «Euroregion», development of pedestrian-tracking and cycling infrastructure and construction of an observation tower on the territory of Truskavets-Oriv-Boryslav-Skhidnytsia region. The overall goal of the projects is to promote and preserve the natural heritage by improving the tourist infrastructure, creating tourist products that will strengthen partnerships and improve the image and tourist attractiveness of the region and Ukraine in general. However, it needs further development and development. In particular, improvement of mechanisms for informing the development of transport infrastructure, expansion of the network of tourist and recreational facilities and tourist information centers, formation of modern engineering, communal, ecological infrastructure of tourist and recreational centers and resorts, creation of tourist products.

An important role in the improvement process is assigned to the formation of a competitive human resource. The priority role in the formation of competitive specialists in the tourism industry should be given to the use of appropriate principles. In particular: human-centeredness, principles of adult learning, focus on the portfolio of competencies, «education of leaders»,

capacity development, self-realization, choice of freedom and creativity, positive thinking, partnership and dialogue, critical thinking. In accordance with today's requirements, the formation of innovation, adaptability and flexibility is also important. At the same time, it is worth noting the importance of introducing a competency-based approach to the normative and practical components of the educational paradigm of training specialists in the tourism industry in accordance with the new realities and challenges of the time. This will eliminate the contradictions between the acquisition of theoretical knowledge by students and their use to solve specific life problems.

Exploring the issue, let's highlight the creation of tourism clusters, the essence of which is that in a certain area are concentrated enterprises of the tourism industry, which interact with each other to create a tourism product. The effectiveness of the creation of tourism clusters is characterized by the partnership of groups of enterprises and government institutions for the joint use of tourism resources, infrastructure, labor market and complementarity. Clusters help accelerate the development of the tourism business, make it possible to increase the competitiveness of the region. It is convinced that the creation of tourist clusters will ensure the quality of tourist services and their range; use of existing infrastructure with the use of fundamentally new technological solutions; Encouraging local small businesses and communities to unite for sustainable tourism development in the Lviv region. It is appropriate to create a tourist cluster of Lviv region, which would include such resorts as: Glass, Skhidnytsia, Morshyn, Truskavets, Velykyi Lyubin, Rozluch, Nemyriv, Slavske, Play, Tysovets and Oryavchyk, Volosyanka, Skole and others. To implement this idea, there are all the necessary prerequisites: in the Lviv region is about 40 % of medicinal mineral springs of Ukraine, respectively, there are recognized both in Ukraine and abroad, resorts. In addition, important factors are the presence of unique climatic conditions and the scientific base of the cluster in the region. In addition to tourism clusters, it is necessary to create infrastructure-innovation clusters that are formed around the system of guaranteed consumption of products and contribute to the improvement of the market of tourist services.

Effective tourism logistics. The use of logistics makes it possible to significantly increase the profitability of the tourism business by reducing costs, as well as increasing the level of logistical coordination of all tourist services. The complex structure of tourism logistics in Lviv region should cover its component, regional and functional structures. The component structure includes:

- logistics of recreational and tourist resources (resource base of tourism);
- logistics of material and technical base of tourism, including logistics of accommodation of tourists (hotel economy) and food (restaurant economy);
- logistics of information infrastructure (information logistics in tourism);
- logistics of transport infrastructure in tourism (logistics of tourist transportation);
- logistics of excursion service;
- logistics of related services in tourism;
- logistics of production and sale of tourist goods.

An effective logistics approach will ensure the development of sustainable tourism, reduce risks and threats to the health and safety of tourists, increase comfort and optimize the tourism market.

Digitalization today is not a development trend, it is a necessity for the functioning of the tourism market. Creation of electronic tours of museums and virtual tours of tourist destinations of Lviv region will provide an opportunity to promote domestic tourism. There is only one open-air virtual museum in the Lviv region – the Museum of Folk Architecture and Life in Lviv «Shevchenkivskyi grove». Which is definitely not enough. In the Lviv region it is necessary to develop such a promising direction, because the region has huge tourist resources that need to be expanded. Active use of digital tools will contribute to the recognition of the region and its promotion in international tourism markets.

The implementation of ID projects for the development of the tourist market of Lviv region is also important. Creating an effective comprehensive mobile application in the Lviv region. In the Lviv region, as well as in Lviv, there is no single universal mobile application that would combine all the necessary information for tourists. There are quite a few mobile applications, however, none of them provide complete information. The tourist needs to download about 10 applications to get all the necessary information, which is definitely not comfortable. That is why it is necessary to create a single mobile application that will satisfy all the requests of tourists and form a positive image of the region.

An important tool for the development of tourist services should be considered the marketing of the tourist region in order to achieve an economically optimal level of tourist attractiveness of the region. It should be noted that the development of the tourism sector is incredibly beneficial for the Lviv region, because tourism directly or indirectly affects the growth of profits, strengthening the economic complex of the region and recovery in many of its areas of business activity. And marketing is one of the important elements that contribute to the promotion of domestic tourism and the revival of future visits. It is convinced that the marketing of the market of tourist services of Lviv region should be aimed at solving the following tasks:

- analysis of tourist resources of the territory;
- analysis of the state and expectations of the main subjects of marketing of the territory (government, business, local population);
- identification and analysis of the most attractive for the territory segments of the tourist market;
- analysis of strengths and weaknesses of the territory;
- analysis of the competitive environment;
- development of a comprehensive tour product of the region that will meet the needs of tourists;
- formation and management of the brand and image of the territory;
- creation of new and improvement of existing attractions of the tourist region;
- development and implementation of a system of marketing communications (promotion) of the tourist region;
- formation and support of strategic partnership of government, business and local population for successful development of the territory;
- increasing the investment attractiveness of the region in the field of tourism.

This research provided an opportunity to form useful innovations in the mechanism of optimizing the market of tourist services that will promote the development of domestic tourism and revive future visits to Lviv region, in particular, and Ukraine in general (as shown in Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. The mechanism of improvement of competitiveness of the market of tourist services (author's development)

Therefore, taking into account the above positions, it is possible to say that the proposed ways to optimize the market of tourist services can be used to increase the level of competitiveness of the market of tourist services in Lviv region and Ukraine in general. In the context of transformational changes in the socio-economic situation, the proposed improvement mechanism can be supplemented and changed.

7. SWOT-analysis of research results

Strengths. The strengths of the study the identification of a mechanism for improvement the competitiveness of the market of tourist services, which will ensure:

- the implementation of safe hospitality; development of clusters in the region, which will improve the quality of tourist services and increase their range;
- introduction of effective promotion, namely dissemination of information about tourist opportunities of Lviv region, both at the national and international levels to promote the tourist brand of the city, increase tourist flows and increase the length of stay of tourists in the city;
- implementation of project ID, efficient logistics, marketing technologies; development and modernization of tourist infrastructure;
- implementation of the formation of a competitive human resource.

Weaknesses. It is not an opportunity to implement the proposed mechanism for optimizing the market of tourist services in the Lviv region due to the crisis quarantine situation in full.

Opportunities. The results of the study will ensure the effective development and modernization of the market of tourist services in the Lviv region and will ensure the tourist attractiveness of the region and Ukraine in general.

Threats. Achieving the improvement of the market of tourist services is possible only with state support and a comprehensive approach to the implementation of improvement. This requires effective public administration, economic support, effective regulatory support and favorable socio-economic conditions.

8. Conclusions

1. The state and main characteristics of tourist and recreational potential of domestic tourism are analyzed on the example of Lviv region. During the research it was pointed out that Lviv region is known for its diverse and unique monuments of history, architecture and culture, rich natural conditions. In particular, attention is focused on the development of cultural, educational, health, skiing, scientific and educational, religious, hunting, rural, ecological, ethnic, sports, health, recreation and entertainment tourism as priority areas for optimizing the market of tourist services.

2. Using the results of the study, the author's improvement mechanism was formed, namely: ways of improve (as shown in Fig. 2) → resources (effective public administration, economic support, modernization of tourism infrastructure, competitive professionals) → actions (investment, improvement, incentives, support) collaboration, implementation of digitalization, introduction of innovation, ensuring effective promotion) → competitive market of tourist services in accordance with today's requirements. It is substantiated

that the implementation of the proposed mechanism will promote the development of domestic tourism on the basis of sustainable development of the tourism industry.

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